

Aussie, Aussie, Aussie! Puff, Puff, Pass! A deep dive into the legal dope debate down under

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Executive Summary

This study describes localised Australian opinions towards legalising marijuana for adult use by examining user generated content in the Twittersphere.

Australia has not legalised recreational marijuana, however, the majority of Australian origin Twitter content would indicate otherwise. Many consumers perceive it not as a drug, but as a lifestyle. Its organic nature makes it the least harmful substance on the Alcohol and Other Drugs (AOD) spectrum.

Australians largely trust the content circulated by news media outlets and although media and communications standards exist to regulate the industry, political advocacy has popularised "news" platforms such as Twitter. The two-way platform attracts both media and public attention so the way these stakeholders use the platform to influence public opinion and recreational marijuana policy is studied.

Tweets published by Australian media, researchers, and policy makers, in conjunction with selected feedback from receivers, may be used to forecast the direction and likelihood of legalisation in Australia.

A content analysis of 88 tweets from 100 users examines the emerging national and regional discourse regarding marijuana policy. The results highlight opportunities for optimised content marketing that can be used to support advocacy campaigns.

In parallel with and counter to much public advocacy via platforms such as Twitter, policymakers continue to invest in media campaigns and research designed to deter or defer marijuana use to perpetuate the stigma associated with marijuana use rather than normalise it because this would imply that cannabis should have never been criminalised in the first place.

Keywords: Cannabis legalisation, Drug policy, Discourse analysis, Twitter, Australia

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Introduction

The recreational marijuana policy landscape in Australia is evolving because Australian attitudes towards marijuana legalisation are changing ([Roy Morgan 2019](#)). “Histories of drug use are often disguised forms of policy advocacy” ([Hall 2013, 1351](#)) and this research is designed to reduce the gap between research and policy ([Ritter 2011](#)). Public opinion research is used to inform changes to drug policy (Makkai and McAllister 1992; [Matthew-Simmons, Love and Ritter 2008](#)) because in democratic societies like Australia, it is vital that the government is seen to be listening to the needs of its constituents to maintain good standing. The federal government is the principal investor in research designed to better understand Australian attitudes and behaviours towards issues such as drug use and legalisation. As evidence is only ever one driver of policy, it is important to understand how public opinion is shaped by the media.

Research from a 38-country survey by the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism at the University of Oxford identifies Australians as the “lightest” news consumers, and the fourth most likely nation to rely on just one source to access news ([Fisher et al. 2019a](#); [Fisher et al. 2019b](#)). Therefore the quality of information circulated by authorities influences public opinion (Lenton and Ovenden 1996; [Hughes et al. 2011](#)). Public consultation is necessary to warrant changes to cannabis control measures, and preliminary research revealed no extant studies have empirically assessed Australian attitudes towards legal cannabis based on news content published by Australian authorities on social media. Social media networks are significant supplementary communication channels for authorities seeking to extend the reach of their messages to audiences with different communication preferences; and encourage participation in the discussion.

Twitter is a “microblogging and social networking service” and is currently the number one news application on the Apple App Store, followed by Reddit and the ABC ([2020](#)). For the purposes of this study, it was anticipated that Twitter could yield deeper insights than less trustworthy sources such as Facebook ([Roy Morgan 2019](#)). This study describes localised Australian opinions towards legalising marijuana for adult use by examining user generated content in the Twittersphere. Tweets published by Australian media, researchers, and policy makers, in conjunction with selected feedback from receivers, may be used to forecast the direction and likelihood of legalisation in Australia.

It is important to distinguish between legalisation and decriminalisation in Australia to better understand how Australians truly feel about cannabis control to the same degree as alcohol or tobacco because that is what legalisation means here and in other places around the world. Twitter provides opportunities for a more accurate, inclusive, and diverse range of responses which aims to address non-sampling errors highlighted in the quality statements of existing studies to develop a more pragmatic view of the issue. Social media allows users to control the narrative on their terms, as opposed to the media who have been known to use rhetoric techniques to persuade audiences to see the world as they do. Historically one-way information

distribution channels have given the news media outlets more control over how information is packaged for processing.

The decision to decriminalise marijuana is not new to Australia but the decision to frame it as legalisation is concerning, especially given the average Australian news consumer behaviour ([Fisher et al. 2019a](#); [Fisher et al. 2019b](#)). This report highlights the limitations of individual data sources, and the incremental gain of bringing data sources together in the Twittersphere. Primary data sources include national and regional mainstream and independent news media outlets, researchers, regulators, and pro-legalisation and anti-legalisation representatives. These primary “significant others” persuade secondary data sources to participate in the debate, and engage audiences that are registered users.

User engagement translates to a participatory culture and collaborative communications co-create context. “Significant others” ([Green 2010, quoted in Allagui and Breslow 2016, 21](#)) persuade audiences to identify with content and react. This meaningful exchange cultivates a depth of knowledge that cannot be acquired from a single source survey or one-way media study ([Barratt et al. 2015](#)). User generated content is globalised, peer reviewed and readily accessible for public opinion research.

Background

Marijuana plant species include *Cannabis indica*, *Cannabis sativa*, and *Cannabis ruderalis*. Hemp is known as low-THC and remains to be one of the most useful substances known to people with industrial applications spanning well beyond nutrition, textiles, and eco-construction. “God’s gift to mankind” ([what do you care 2003](#)) is the top definition of the substance according to [Urban Dictionary](#) (2020). Many consumers perceive it not as a drug, but as a lifestyle. Its organic nature makes it the least harmful substance on the AOD spectrum.

While Australians continue to mull over adult cannabis control, it is important to be aware of the scope of social terminology applied in reference to the substance to avoid semantic battles in a conceptual war of drugs being bad and medicines being good. These include Green, Bush, Bud, “Pot, Grass, Weed, Reefer, Joint, MaryJane, Acapulco gold, Rope, Mull, Cone, Spliff, Dope, Hydro, Bhang, Ganja, Hash, and Chronic” ([AIHW 2019](#)).

Australia is the latest G20 nation seen to be legalising marijuana for adult use after a media frenzy ensued on and offline on September 25, 2019. News regarding recreational marijuana policy in the Australian Capital Territory (ACT) spread like wildfire, making international headlines the very same day reporting that the ACT legalised recreational cannabis and is the first jurisdiction in Australia to do so but this simply is not true. The [Drugs of Dependence \(Personal Cannabis Use\) Amendment Bill 2018](#) allows Canberrans over the age of 18 to legally possess, organically cultivate and consume their personal supply in a private dwelling under strict conditions. Despite media reports, policy changes such as this are not new for Australia.

Similar to Washington DC's policy, only without their all-important seed sharing initiative ([David and Stein 2015](#)), the ACT's new laws came into effect on January 31, 2020. The supply reduction strategy decriminalises sections of the *Criminal Code 2002* for Canberran adults possessing up to 50 grams of dried marijuana or up to 150 grams of fresh cannabis, naturally growing up to two plants per adult or four plants per household, when kept out of reach and exposure to children, and consumed in a private place. Roy Morgan ([2019](#)) attribute the shift in Australian attitudes to the well-publicised trend towards marijuana legalisation in the Americas, however academics, members of the public and politicians have been credited for deepening the worldwide debate (Lenton and Overton 1996; [Makkai and McAllister 1993](#); Shapiro 1994; [Single 1989](#)) long before Twitter even existed. "The nanny state problem is not confined to just puritanism, prohibition and an inability to understand evidence-based policy. Every time those in love with their own expertise seek to regulate what people buy or put in their mouths, they forget that the people who purchase and the people who vote are the same people" ([Leyonhjelm 2015](#)).

69 medicinal cannabis licences have been issued by the Office of Drug Control (ODC) since the federal government amended the [Narcotic Drugs Act 1967](#) on February 24, 2016 ([Commonwealth of Australia 2019](#)). The ODC estimate 7,196 patients have been authorised access to medicinal cannabis products in Australia and over 10,000 prescriptions have been written ([Commonwealth of Australia 2019](#)). Fast forward almost three years to November 27, 2018 when Greens Senator, Richard Di Natale submitted the [Australian Cannabis Agency Bill 2018](#), calling for an Act to establish the Australian Cannabis Agency to regulate the production and distribution of recreational cannabis in the ACT and NT. The supplementary [Explanatory Memorandum](#) details a range of pro-legalisation arguments.

On June 18, 2019, North Metropolitan Labor backbencher, Fiona Patten presented a Legislative Council Electronic Petition signed by 1,655 Victorians in support of "Cannabis Decriminalisation" to the house on June 18, 2019. These citizens concur "that it is immoral for the Government to tell people whether they can smoke cannabis" and that "the Government should treat adults as adults and not baby them" (Parliament of Victoria 2019, 21). The cohort highlight the economic benefits of legalising recreational cannabis in the State of Colorado in the USA, and suggest the government use this as an example to support the introduction of "a Bill for the legalisation of recreational cannabis" in Victoria (Parliament of Victoria 2019, 21).

Roy Morgan ([2019](#)) research shows that marijuana legalisation advocates are "up 9% points", and critics are down 7% to 49%. If the 9% of Australians that are undecided about their position on the issue are converted to support legalisation, this should mean most Australians (51%) would be pro-legalisation ([Roy Morgan 2019](#)). Therefore, the emerging national discourse on recreational marijuana legalisation in Australia requires ongoing research. Roy Morgan ([2018](#)) suggest using news website visitation data in conjunction with Single Source data to inform targeted tactical communication strategies.

Literature Review

The information landscape has undergone a digital transformation over the past decade so the breadth of strategies applied to public opinion research studies that have examined societal preferences for cannabis policies are reviewed. These include public opinion data derived from grey literature, surveys, traditional news media, and social media studies. Studies of public opinion about personal drug use and attitudes towards legalisation in Australia and other countries have traditionally been survey and media based, however two-way symmetrical communication channels, such as Twitter provide real-time public research data that can be utilised for insight, targeting and evaluation.

A comprehensive review of existing literature reveals that a large volume of the evidence is communicated through grey literature (Booth, Sutton and Papaioannou 2016). [Makkai and McAllister \(1993\)](#) and Lenton and Ovensen (1996, 784) argue "the measurement of public opinion about legal options concerning cannabis use, and documenting and disseminating these findings to the general public and the politicians whom they vote for, is likely to be a powerful way of affecting the debate on this issue." The way data is collected and circulated by authorities influences the opinions of others by design.

National Drug Strategy Household Survey (NDSHS) data quality statements published by the Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW) confirm the degree of geographic detail published differs. "Data are generally published at the national level with a selection of data published at the State/Territory, Remoteness Area and Primary Health Network levels" ([AIHW 2020](#)). Therefore, it is important to review the different research strategies used in studies of public opinion that generate findings used to inform decisions regarding social policy-related public health matters such as legalising marijuana use (see Appendix Table 1). The rigorous research conducted by the Drug Policy Modelling Program (DPMP) that is subsequently published in a Monograph Series by the National Drug and Alcohol Research Centre (NDARC) provides the most current and coherent analysis of drug-related research funded by the Australian government.

Research priorities for assessing the effects of legalising non-medical use in America are highlighted by Hall et al. ([2019, 1587](#)) but it is too early to evaluate these as the semi-legal industry is in its infancy. The existing research is segmented by the different methods used by different data providers to better understand how these strategies depict public opinion data used to inform decisions surrounding marijuana legalisation. Computer assisted sampling and data collection methods are identified across the breadth of research.

Survey based studies

New research from Roy Morgan "shows increasing numbers of Australians across all age groups want to legalise marijuana" (see Figure 1), however the findings support the theory that

legalisation is unlikely until the local residents that are anti-legalisation become the minority ([Matthew-Smith, Love and Ritter 2008](#); [Roy Morgan 2019](#)). By this logic, according to the Australian Broadcast Corporation's 2019 Australia Talks Survey, it would be legalised in Tasmania (51%). "High school and household surveys in Australia, Canada, and the USA provide the most comprehensive data on long-term trends" ([Hall et al. 2019, 1581](#)). Surveys that target local or state populations to better understand the impact of changes within the community may be used to make assumptions about that population however, they cannot be used to represent the opinions of the nation ([Matthew-Simmons, Love and Ritter 2008](#)).

Comparisons of data from previous iterations of the same study should be observed with caution due to differences in scope, collection methodology and design. Perceptions of behaviour identified should also be considered conservative as respondents "tend to underestimate actual consumption levels (Stockwell et al. 2004 quoted in AIHW 2020). Affected communities ([Lancaster, Sutherland and Ritter 2014](#); [Lancaster, Ritter and Stafford 2012](#)) are underrepresented by sample design as exclusions include homeless persons; people residing in non-private dwellings and institutional settings; and residents of Jervis Bay, Christmas Island and Cocos Island ([AIHW 2013](#)). Some of the voices of people who use illicit drugs that may be marginalised in the marijuana policy debate are represented by NDARC's Illicit Drug Reporting System ([IDRS](#)) and Ecstasy and Related Drugs Reporting System ([EDRS](#)).

Shanahan, Gerard and Ritter ([2014](#)) used figures sourced from NSW literature to inform the development of three socially acceptable marijuana policy options that account for trade-offs between the multiple wide ranging social harms and the legal status of cannabis. This was the first known Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) survey applied to the area of illicit drugs policy, the design of which could be applied to determine the optimal cannabis law for any given society by testing "what if" scenarios. Existing research suggests that individuals need to be aware of the current legal status of cannabis in their jurisdiction ([Fetherston and Lenton 2005](#); [Erikson, van der Maas and Hathaway 2013](#)) to interpret public survey results. Many survey-based studies perpetuate Australia's ambiguity issues by framing questions to support cannabis decriminalisation rather than legalisation in alcohol and tobacco terms.

Media based studies

McGinty et al ([2016](#)) found that media coverage of the issue was concentrated in areas where recreational consumption, production and distribution had been legalised. By legalising the drug it removes the stigmas associated by the prohibition era and normalises discussion across news outlets. Australia has not legalised the drug for recreational use but the terms "legal cannabis" and "legal marijuana" are likely to be divisive to the debate. News media coverage of the issue would appear negative when the information circulated communicates consequences rather than benefits of usage ([Hughes et al. 2011](#)).

Framing the substance as an illicit drug versus a medicine ([Sznitman and Lewis 2015](#)) portrays

recreational use as dangerous but tobacco and alcohol are licit drugs that cannot be depicted as medicine.

If the relationship between news media coverage of marijuana and adolescent use of the drug ([Stryker 2003](#)) was a concern in Australia, a news story about legalising marijuana would not be linked to a story that unveils Mattel's new gender-neutral Barbie ([Nine News Perth 2019](#)).

The largest known media content analysis of reporting on illicit drug issues in Australia examined 4,397 articles from 11 major Australian daily and weekend newspapers from 2003 to 2008. Hughes, Lancaster and Spicer ([2011](#)) found that less bias existed when everyday patterns of reporting were analysed. Therefore, it is important to understand the breadth of data-driven insights used by Australian news sources to convey expectations and attribute positive or negative value to the ongoing discussion surrounding marijuana legislative reform in different jurisdictions beyond periods of heightened awareness.

Few Australian media content analyses have included data from the previous decade. This research contributes to existing literature regarding the influential role the media play in shaping public policy, relative to the target population, considering legalising marijuana for adult use.

Social media-based studies

Daniulaityte et al ([2017](#)) used the Twitter API and Drug eTrends database to determine that states with less restrictive policies conveyed more positive sentiment thereby highlighting the importance of Twitter data as a means to assess public opinion in the context of varying policy environments.

No extant studies of public opinion have assessed news media coverage of legal cannabis in Australia on social media. The present study fills this research gap by analysing how the Australian media depict marijuana policy given their professional responsibility to report objectively; and how the public interact with these users, their "news" and other users in the public online exchange between key stakeholders on Twitter. This research will identify stakeholders that use relevant research to provide context to audiences. This should provide some indication as to how localised audiences interpret existing policies, and if they are for or against legalisation, recognising that decriminalisation is not the same thing.

Scoping studies

An Australian early warning system (EWS) feasibility study prepared by the NDARC for the Federal Minister for Health in 2017 recognises the "opportunity for more systematic and timely triangulation of existing data to rapidly assess and identify emerging illicit drug trends in Australia" ([Peacock et al. 2020, 7](#)). "286 routinely collected and collated data sources measuring illicit drug use, harms, and/or market features in Australia" are identified, 76 met feasibility criteria, and 53 feasibility applications were pending ([Peacock et al. 2020, 7](#)). The scoping review

confirms that other data sources should include social media networks such as Twitter to identify drug-related posts, and outcomes (use; health harms; illicit availability; illicit price) using the Twitter API to scrape, clean and collate for analysis of data specific to the Australian context.

Another Australian scoping review by Lee, Roehrer, and Cummings ([2017](#)) explores the literature on information overload in lay adult and adolescent consumers of health-related information. This study did not exclude user generated content prior to November 8, 2017 in response to Twitter doubling the character limits of tweets. The quality of health-related information is more important than the quantity.

Research objectives / questions

If successful social media campaigns generally adhere to at least one of “the PARC principles for success: participatory (interact with the target audience), authentic (conversing without forced attitudes or a false, or overtly commercial, demeanour), resourceful (provide audience with helpful information and, with respect to the use of social media, a variety of unique and entertaining and informative channels and methods of engagement), and credible” (Barker, Barker, Bormann and Neher 2013, quoted in [Allagui and Breslow 2016, 22](#)), how do national and regional news media outlets, policymakers, researchers and the public mediate the knowledge these data sources share on Twitter; and how these insights should be applied to influence recreational marijuana policy across Australia.

The [National Drug Strategy 2017-2026](#) classifies cannabis as a priority substance, with nationally agreed priority actions and populations. Whether the data collected confirms that any other “priority substances” are used to frame marijuana policy messaging will be meaningful given evidence-based research promotes the health benefits associated with marijuana for medicinal use ([© Commonwealth of Australia \(Department of Health\) 2017](#)). “The Strategy was informed by a national consultation process throughout 2015, which included key informant interviews, online survey feedback and stakeholder forums” ([© Commonwealth of Australia \(Department of Health\) 2017](#)).

The way data sources contextualise the message for the audiences is expected to highlight their position on recreational marijuana legalisation. News that provides both national and jurisdictional evidence is also significant as this serves to broaden the content circulated overall ([Hyshka et al. 2017](#)), and social media provides opportunities for insight, targeting and evaluation of data sources, content and engaged audiences.

Methodology

Research Design

Qualitative primary data was collected through observation of publicly available and relevant tweets circulated by the Twitter users followed, together with audience feedback (secondary data source). A total of 88 tweets from 41 users who published content that featured the term,

"legal", and any of the terms, "marijuana" or "cannabis" or "weed" or "dope" or "pot" were extracted from Twitter. Manual data extraction method was expected to be demanding so dataset extraction alternatives including the Twitter API, and Google Chrome extensions including Web Scraper and Datap (AI-powered web scraping) were meticulously considered. One of the major benefits of this research strategy is that more data is freely available for collection and analysis.

Sampling and data collection method

Preliminary research into the national dialogue surrounding recreational marijuana legalisation in Australia initially involved searching Informit and Factiva for Australian media coverage of the issue. This Boolean search strategy was limited to any of the terms, "marijuana*" or "cannabis*", and any of the terms, "recreation*" or "non-medic*" or "retail" or "adult" or "personal", and any of the terms, "legal*" or "legis*" or "law" or "policy"; and "Australia*" (Australia or Australian or Australians). These findings highlighted several Australian news outlets reporting on the issue at national and regional levels, that were determined to be influential, and therefore warranted inclusion in the sample of users followed for further analysis on Twitter. Disparity in cross-platform audiences was anticipated due to individual communication preferences, therefore the unique Twitter following of users observed for the purposes of this study did not uniformly justify inclusion in the study.

Trusted authorities are key contributors to the conversation as they are expected to share credible knowledge to elevate the debate on Twitter. The ABC, SBS, Schwartz media, and Macquarie media (acquired by Nine in 2018 and recently rebranded as Nine Radio) were the only networks to return a positive Net Trust Score (NTS) in the 2019 MEDIA Net Trust Survey ([Roy Morgan 2019](#)). Other participating media conglomerates included News Corp Australia, Australian Community Media, Ten, Seven and Seven West Media. Twitter accounts of popular print, broadcast and internet news sources were selected to reflect how the regional and national media depict the issue on the social media/news platform and how audiences respond to the news.

Roy Morgan ([2020](#)) Australian Newspaper Readership research data was used to identify high circulation national and regional print news sources for inclusion in this study so the most congruent Twitter account for each of these publications were feasible for inclusion.

Independent Australian users that met the feasibility criteria were included to represent the advocate, detractor, farmer, and media regulator. Academics, members of the public and politicians should deepen the Australian debate as they have done universally (Lenton and Overton 1996; [Makkai and McAllister 1993](#); Shapiro 1994; [Single 1989](#)). Policy makers were also represented in the users followed on Twitter as public servants from agencies including the Department of Health and Department of Justice at both state and federal levels frequently feature as experts in the news content published/aired by mainstream media. The authority of

each affiliated Twitter account was authenticated by searching the "name and locality of the source + twitter" in Google, and in some cases, verifying official accounts from the Twitter badge/link embedded on the sources owned websites.

This non-probability purposive sampling method was used to limit the scope of research to relevant content published by 88/112 Twitter users which included 22/29 National news media outlets, 40/51 Regional news outlets, 5/7 National research authorities, 5/9 Federal Government and 14 State Government entities, Legalise Now, Drug Free Australia, Australian Communications and Media Authority, and National Farmers' Federation.

Data selection

The "Top", "Latest", "People", "Photos", and "Video" results from the sample of "People you follow" "Anywhere" as opposed to "Near Me" that published tweets featuring the term "legal" and any of the terms, "marijuana" or "cannabis" or "weed" or "dope" or "pot" were collected during Q2 2020.

Of the 88 users that were followed in phase one, 37 returned results for 82 tweets (42% response rate) including the terms "legal" and "marijuana" or "cannabis" or "weed". This included five tweets (6% of total responses) from Twitter user, Legalise Now to develop a basic understanding of Australian pro-legalisation advocacy efforts. This user and their tweets were excluded from the collective analysis to address issues of bias when drawing conclusions from a sample that are somewhat expected to report without bias. Similarly, Drug Free Australia was selected to represent anti-legalisation activism but despite featuring in the embedded content of the extract ([news.com.au 2019](#)), no tweets met the search criteria. Only one other tweet published by ABC Adelaide ([2019](#)) was excluded from the study as the post was related to industrial hemp which is not intended for recreational or medicinal consumption. The details of each tweet returned using this search strategy were collected for further analysis.

Data analysis

Messages circulated by primary data sources were categorised as medicinal or recreational to distinguish between public opinions expressed in the Twittersphere regarding medicinal marijuana, and marijuana for adult use. If this was not confirmed by the language used in the tweet alone the embedded rich content was reviewed to confirm the context. Tweets and embedded content from primary and secondary data sources were analysed to describe arguments in favour of recreational marijuana legalisation; arguments against recreational marijuana legalisation; options for regulating recreational use of marijuana; the number of tweets per state; the number of likes, tweets and comments; the number of images posted; the number of videos posted; and the number and types of hashtags used.

For the purposes of this study, tweets with broken embedded links to articles on the user's owned website that could not be conclusively determined to be positive or negative were

classified as no argument. Tweets were classified as balanced when both the tweet and embedded link were found to report on the issue without bias for or against legalisation. Identical (and near-identical) tweets from the national and state arm of Australian news media outlets were analysed to better understand how engaged audiences interact with the same content in different ways depending on the user/publisher.

Results

A total of 82 tweets from 37 users were initially collected for further analysis. The data collected was published over a period of almost six years. The 20 "Top" and "Latest" results were recorded along with 45 tweets under "Photos" and 23 under "Videos". No results were returned under "People". 77 tweets from 36 Australian news media outlets were extracted during phase one for collective analysis. Preliminary results indicate a lack of state media representation from news outlets in the Northern Territory and Tasmania, despite national news coverage of the developing situation in Tasmania ([Financial Review 2015](#); [ABC News 2016](#); [ABC News 2019](#);). 48% of tweets were regarding medicinal use (N=37) and 52% were regarding recreational use (N=42).

Although a discourse analysis could not be conducted, the debate surrounding legalisation of medicinal marijuana has affected public perception of recreational marijuana in a positive way. Of the national, state and territory policy makers and academics that were followed for their ability to influence changes to marijuana legalisation, 0% engaged in the exchange of ontological and epistemological psycho-social subjective constructs regarding recreational marijuana use or legalisation in the Twittersphere.

The legal marijuana debate was led by state based talks regarding legalising medicinal marijuana from [7News Adelaide](#) and [Nine News Sydney](#) in July 2014, and [Perth Now](#) in October 2014. 10% of all tweets were published across the sample for 2015, 87.5% were determined to be medicinal. Canberra Times ([2015](#)) led state and national coverage of the recreational market in March with the US-led and pro-recreational legalisation tweet "[Pot luck: Americans line up for biggest legal marijuana giveaway](#)". This was the only 2015 tweet that registered zero engagement (comments, retweets, or likes), however the embedded link was found to be broken.

Roy Morgan ([2018](#)) confirm news.com.au has the largest audience in Australia and their only tweet "[The backlash has begun after one Australian city made cannabis legal for personal use. Critics say the drug can lead to psychotic disorders.](#)" ([news.com.au 2019](#)) yielded the highest response rate overall, with 55 comments, 20 retweets, and 46 likes. The response to the rich content embedded was also the highest recorded for the sample. "What cannabis does to your brain" ([Graham 2019](#)), published on their owned website, generated 140 comments.

50% of tweets and embedded links from Australian news media outlets were pro-recreational legalisation (N=37), this included 36% of national news authorities and 39% regional media

outlets. 7% of tweets were categorised as anti-rec overall, this included 27% of all national news tweets and 0% from regional media outlets. 50% of tweets from the ACT and WA were pro-recreational legalisation. 21% of all recreational tweets presented arguments from multiple perspectives and 33% of rec tweets reported the news without bias (no argument/neutral).

Aristotle's rhetorical triangle provides the theoretical framework for this study and semantics are a major concern highlighted by the research. Tweets from Australian media were found to use semantics to perpetuate myths of legalisation. For the purposes of this study it was assumed that audiences were expected to decode tweets using the embedded links. The lack of context the primary data sources provided drives secondary data sources to their owned websites. Neither ABC nor SBS were found to provide the same opportunity other primary data sources provide for commentary on articles published on their website in favour of knowledge sharing options (Facebook, Twitter etc.) that encourage participation in the ongoing discussion on a public forum.

Twitter search results for "decriminalisation" and any of the terms, "cannabis", "marijuana", "weed", "dope" or "pot" date back to April 2012, two years prior to the "legal" debate extracted for the purposes of this study. More participation was superficially observed in these results from research authorities (NDARC and NDRI), and Tasmania (The Examiner and ABC Hobart).

Discussion

The effects of liberalisation are yet to be experienced in Australia. Australian news media outlets depict the sensory world to share the adult experience qualities from an international perspective.

Political implications

The ABC, 10News First, Nine News, and 7NEWS conglomerates were all found to circulate the same information across their suite of Twitter accounts. The engagement metrics reflect the level of local interest in the issue, and the likelihood of more coverage of the issue. The way news is dispersed in the Twittersphere implies that some states prioritise emerging state discourse from the nation's capital before the ACT publishes related tweets. Canberra Times was the first user to tweet about recreational marijuana in Australia with a US-led and pro-recreational legalisation tweet in March 2015. This was the only 2015 tweet that registered zero engagement (comments, retweets, or likes). The article embedded in "[Pot luck: Americans line up for biggest legal marijuana giveaway](#)" was broken and a Google search of the headline found it published on Australia's second most popular news website, the Sydney Morning Herald ([Roy Morgan 2018](#)). SMH was included in the 88 users initially followed, but they were not represented in the data extract. Davis and Stein ([2015](#)) discuss the seed sharing initiative implemented as part of Washington D.C. legalisation of possession and cultivation of cannabis for personal use. An initiative that has not been raised as a regulatory option in Australia.

Managerial implications

Researchers with programming backgrounds, and projects with additional time and funding could be expected to adopt a more technical approach so the sampling method could be improved. "Cross-validation of sources (i.e., checking for similar findings across all indicators of the same outcome) and triangulation (i.e., combination of findings from various indicators) can address these limitations, and are critical to ensuring sensitivity to, and confidence in, detection of emerging trends" ([Peacock et al. 2020, 9](#)).

Ethical implications

Although media standards exist to regulate reporting standards, quality management can become problematic when governed by the terms of an external platform. The issue commonly raised across the breadth of international and domestic literature is that more research is needed to understand the implications of use and legalisation. The ethical complexities of this could be a secondary reason for legalising medicinal cannabis but in order to justify arguments against legalisation of cannabis for adults, more allowances should be made to address this research gap. Researchers from Monash University are conducting field based recreational marijuana research in Nimbin. "Australia's first naturalistic study of long-term cannabis use on the brain and mental health" will assess "how their brain has responded over time to the levels of chemical compounds, known as cannabinoids, contained within the typical marijuana they use" ([Tydd 2019](#)).

Commercial implications

There are 440 pharmaceutical product manufacturing businesses in Australia that generate \$8.4 billion revenue and turnover \$814.3 million profit (Richardson 2019). It is predicted that these businesses would suffer from legalisation as more Australians turn to alternative medicines to treat a number of health issues. Legalisation can provide opportunities for medicinal cannabis businesses to expand to serve the rec market and serve to demystify issues raised regarding usage and discredit the opinions of stakeholders that hinge their anti-legalisation stance on the health risks circulated by the media.

Public implications

Issues derived from media fragmentation, research designs, and circulation of information are expressed by the media, the public, and government agencies, however this knowledge is not equally shared. This study highlighted the difficulties associated with individual and collective capacities to correctly interpret reliable, accurate and timely data regarding the issue.

Twitter provides push and pull marketing opportunities for real time audience feedback (UGC). The all-important context within which these exchanges are made determines the quality of communication shared. Semiotics play a large part in the interpretative process and reactions to tweets. This research is useful for the strategic development of communications strategies to optimise public education campaign collateral.

Recommendation

User engagement translates to a participatory culture, therefore “participation and collaboration should be the mantra of online public relations in social media environments” (Valentini and Kruckeberg 2012, quoted in [Allagui and Breslow 2016, 21](#)). The loss of control concept could be explored by primary data sources that attribute the value of the message to the content creator rather than just the publisher. Transparency fosters trust, technology enables innovation, and consistency is needed regarding knowledge management despite any capacity for Freedom of Information (FOI) requests.

The Australian National Advisory Council on Alcohol and Drugs (ANACAD), or A.P.S.A.D as represented in the primary data sample, is identified as the “principal expert advisory body to the Australian Government on issues relating to alcohol and other drugs (AOD), providing “confidential, strategic, evidence-based advice” since 2014 (Commonwealth of Australia Department of Health 2020). The research developed and distributed as part of the DPMP Monograph Series should be maintained and marketed as it is updated. The public pay for the bulk of the research so they should be kept as informed as the government elected to represent them in the decision-making process. Each monograph should be updated as policy changes are implemented at state and federal levels, or as the body of literature increases. For example, the summary of police and court diversion programs that can be employed for use/possession offences in Australia, by type and state/territory ([Hughes et al. 2019, 3](#)) below, should be updated and circulated to reflect the state of decriminalisation effective January 31, 2020 in the ACT. This best practice enables audiences to interpret the current data correctly and respond accordingly. By explicitly guaranteeing timeliness, accessibility, interpretability, relevance, accuracy, and coherence, researchers could rely on the data and allocate more time to primary data collection and analysis so more conclusive findings may be determined in the future.

Limitations

Both sampling and non-sampling errors should be considered when interpreting results. Although researcher participation in this study is low, some interpretation was necessary to code the content as recreational or medicinal; and pro-legalisation, anti-legalisation, balanced or no argument. Tweets were not interpreted at face value due to issues regarding semantics. Tweets that did not differentiate “legal cannabis” and “legal marijuana” by usage (medicinal or recreational) were cross-checked against the embedded rich content to identify the context of the message circulated by primary data sources. There were instances during data collection, cross-checking, and interpretation where the engagement metrics recorded for a tweet did not correlate with the replies available for documentation. Geographic and demographic data was not extracted for secondary data sources for the purposes of this study. Despite the potential for human error during the data collection process, additional cross-checking was carried out as the research methodology evolved. The manual extraction method was determined to be more reliable after reviewing other techniques such as Twitter’s API and AI-powered web scraper

Google Chrome extension, Datap.

Future Research

Professors, lawyers, users, doctors, patients and parents of patients, advocates and critics featured in the content collected during the first phase of this study; and authors of academic literature reviewed, and news reporting in an Australian context should be included in the study sample for future research. The 286 data sources highlighted by the NDARC's VIEWS study would also be expected to publish research in a more timely manner for public knowledge ([Peacock et al, 2020](#)).

Social media networks have the capacity to adapt their technology to meet user needs and therefore are constantly evolving to compete with other platforms. Developer responsiveness creates complexities for longitudinal social-media based research. Twitter doubled the maximum Tweet length from 140 characters to 280 characters on November 8, 2017 to facilitate more expression ([Perez 2017](#)). Although 90% of recreational tweets were available for analysis after this change was implemented, 100% were included to evaluate the emerging discourse on recreational marijuana use and legalisation across regional and national jurisdictions.

Primary data sources were triangulated by geographic region to identify the mood of the media and the content circulating regarding marijuana use and legalisation across Australian states and territories but not all states and territory jurisdictions were represented in the results. Secondary data sources were not segmented by locality so the feedback could not be assigned to the region. As Reddit is the second most popular news platform on the Apple App Store, data retrieved from this website may garner more diverse feedback. A discourse analysis would also be beneficial however this was beyond the scope of this study. Academic representation was restricted to the references cited by the sample. Future research could determine whether scholars cited in this study are active on social media. Social media posts from the academics and journalists identified as part of this study warrant further analysis to explore PR opportunities designed to promote circulation of scholarly content and encourage media interviews with experts.

Correlations between media ownership, research funding, and publicity of scholarly research requires ongoing research.

Although beyond the scope of this study and despite the hurdles for ethical research approval, a comparative study of people with anger management and polydrug dependence and abuse issues should be conducted to prove that when it comes to community harm minimisation strategies, dealing with a population of stoners is much safer than a bunch of raging alcoholics. Driving tests are also recommended for future research, not as a means to trial "RDT" methods, but to evaluate the risk associated with an alcohol-impaired driver and a cannabis-impaired driver, provided both believe they are ok to drive.

Conclusion

Recreational cannabis users will attribute implications of their personal use, such as short term memory loss to the drug, however the opportunity costs do not justify not using the substance. Although international studies highlight negative aspects of heavy usage of high potency marijuana in America, it is not unreasonable to attribute this to a learning curve among consumers. Similar to the learning curve that applies to alcohol intake, individuals must listen to their bodies and respond accordingly. Marijuana is not addictive like alcohol or tobacco but people can become dependent on using it, much like any ongoing medical treatment.

Policymakers continue to invest in research designed to deter or defer marijuana use to perpetuate the stigma associated with marijuana use rather than normalise it because this would imply that cannabis should have never been criminalised in the first place. Any substance affects different people in different ways and people should be aware of any risks associated when trying new things. Adults must take responsibility for themselves rather than allow the government to decide what is best for them. Enculturation around cannabis use is embedded in pop culture. Public education should be embedded in policy development because without context, audiences are expected to form opinions on the issue without all the information necessary to do so.

Just because something is illegal does not mean it is bad for everyone. Ethically speaking, policies are designed to minimise harm but when the policy has been shown to deny positive outcomes it becomes unethical. It is realistic to expect that legalisation would increase use, especially if research methods differ from existing longitudinal designs. The deterrence model theory implemented during the prohibition era failed. The same logic should have been applied to alcohol and tobacco because empirical research confirms their legal status does not minimise harm, therefore the logic behind the decision to legalise these substances ahead of cannabis is questionable.

Excise tax rates in Australia are some of the highest in the world so it would be expected that the same approach would apply to cannabis control in Australia which would mean it may not compete with the price and quality offered by the black market. Users that qualify for prescribed medicinal cannabis are still accessing the product through the black market because the prescribed price is unaffordable for most.

Despite concerns raised regarding the lack of a universal standard for testing drivers for cannabis related impairment, it will still happen, much like medicinal users will still seek access to supply from the black market, because the current system does not meet the needs of consumers. The capacity for the government to control usage contributes to the likelihood of legalisation.

This study concludes that until such time as Australia is ready to establish federal and state

cannabis agencies to regulate the recreational cannabis industry using licensing measures similar to those implemented in response to requests from the majority of electorates regarding medicinal cannabis, it is unlikely that recreational cannabis use will progress from a state of decriminalisation to legalisation. Seed-sharing, cannabis clubs and cafes could be a significant step in any Australian state or territory jurisdiction and a major drawcard for nearby populations. Academic research including empirical studies such as this require publicity to disseminate findings to Australians across news media outlets and social media platforms to encourage public participation in the discussion at national and state levels.

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